

MAIN CLINICAL SIGNS OF NON-REUMATIC MYOCARDITIS IN CHILDREN OF SAMARKAND REGION

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ABSTRACT

In the cardio-rheumatology department of the Samarkand Regional Multidisciplinary Children's Clinical Center, we studied clinical and electrocardiographic analysis of 50 young patients with non-rheumatic myocarditis in the last 2020-2021. 86% of young children with a history of acute respiratory infection. Of the clinical symptoms of non-rheumatic myocarditis, general weakness was 88%, profuse sweating was 86%, cough was 50%, redness of the lips and nose was 58%, and white marble skin was 76%. Heart tones were observed in all patients. "gallop rhythm" was 32%. Tachycardia was 80%, arrhythmia was 14%, extrasystole was 14%, and bradycardia was 4%. From ECG changes: Rhythmic disorders, sinus tachycardia 88%, sinus arrhythmia 12%, extrasystole 14%, sinus bradycardia 6%. Right ventricular hypertrophy was 24%. Hypertrophy of the left ventricle of the heart was observed in 46%. Cardiomegaly was detected in 20%. According to the results of the study, sinus tachycardia was observed in 88% of children from cardiac symptoms, and a decrease in first tone heart rate was observed in 72% of children. According to OA Mutafyan and Yu.M. Belozarov, tachycardia was 65% and 62.5%, respectively. In contrast, symptoms such as bradycardia, arrhythmia, and extrasystole were twice as rare in our studies as reported by Yu.M. Belozarov (2014) and O.A. Mutafyan (2016).

The urgency of the problem. Myocarditis can be seen at different ages, especially among young children. In some cases, mild forms of myocarditis appear without symptoms, so they are not recorded anywhere, which makes it difficult to determine its exact prevalence (N.V. Orlova, T.V. Pariyskaya 2019).

According to data, 24-33% of children may have myocatitis without symptoms (E.Rarillo 2018). According to Yu.M. Belozarov, 10 out of 1000 people have myocarditis (YU.M.

Belozerova 2014). Myocardial damage can be observed in 1-5% of patients with acute viral infection (YU.M. Belozerova 2014).

The mild form of myocardium passes without symptoms, and the severe form leads to heart failure and acute circulatory disorders due to complex heart rhythm disorders (E.N. Amosova 2018, V.S. Prikhodka. 2011).

Clinical manifestations of myocarditis in children are non-specific compared to other diseases, thus it creates difficulties for many practitioners. Currently, anticardiac antibodies are detected in the blood serum of patients with myocarditis (V.P. Krivonostov 2016).

The clinical appearance of myocarditis in children is determined mainly depending on the etiology, distribution, depth and different course of the pathological process. The clinical manifestation of the disease is nonspecific. The mild form of myocarditis passes without symptoms, and the severe form leads to heart failure and acute circulatory disorders as a result of complex heart rhythm disturbances (E.N. Amosova 2012, V.S. Prikhodka i soavt. 2013).

Based on these, one of the urgent tasks of children's cardiology is to determine the features of the modern clinical course of non-rheumatic myocarditis among children of different ages in Samarkand city and their distribution.

Research object and subject: We studied clinical and electrocardiographic analyzes of 100 early-aged children with non-rheumatic carditis in the cardio-rheumatology department of the multidisciplinary children's clinical center of Samarkand region during last 2019-2022 years.

The purpose of the work: to study the current clinical picture of non-rheumatic carditis in children of early age and to conduct a comparative analysis of the obtained data with the data presented in the literature.

Tasks of scientific work.

1. To study the current clinical course of non-rheumatic carditis in early age children and to determine the diagnostic criteria.
2. Conducting a comparative analysis of the results obtained in the course of research with information in the literature.

Investigation results. Our investigations showed that 90% of children with non-rheumatic myocarditis had an acute respiratory infection in their anamnesis. Analyzing the perinatal anamnesis, 82% of miscarriages, 46% of pregnancy gestosis.

When examining the perimorbid background of early-aged children with non-rheumatic myocarditis, it was found that 92% of them developed anemia, 36% developed exudative catarrhal diathesis and hypotrophy, and 30% developed lymphatic-hypoplastic diathesis. Among the clinical symptoms of non-rheumatic myocarditis, general weakness was 92%, profuse sweating 86%, cough 70%, wheezing around the lips and nose 78%, skin white marble color 76%. Murmurs of heart sounds were observed in all patients. "gallop" rhythm was 32%. Tachycardia was 80%, arrhythmia 14%, extrasystole 14%, bradycardia 4%.

3.2.1 Table. Frequency of clinical symptoms in non-rheumatic carditis children by age (%).

Clinical symptoms	3-7 years		7-12 years		Overall	
	N=4	%	N=14	%	N=50	%

Shortness of breath	0	0	4	8	24	48
Cyanosis around nose and the lips	1	2	6	12	27	78
Profuse sweating	0	0	4	8	29	86
Quick fatigue	2	4	8	16	32	64
Cough	1	2	3	6	24	70
Delay in physical development	0	0	6	12	28	56
Heart - relative border enlargement from the right	0	0	1	2	15	30
From the left	2	4	8	16	14	28
tachycardia	1	2	3	6	29	58
bradycardia	0	0	6	12	7	14
Attenuation of 1 st tone	3	6	12	24	39	78

1. The onset time of the disease was more than 15 days in 40%.
 2. 80% of seriously ill patients were children under 3 years of age.
 3. Among the complaints of adult children, the most common pain symptom is 42%.
 4. Tachycardia was found in 79% of children under 3 years old, 28% in 7-12 years old.
 5. Bradycardia was found in 3% of children under 3 years old, 31% in 7-12 years old.
- In 7-12-year-olds, 28% (4 people) had partial sinus arrhythmia, 42% (6 people) had obvious sinus arrhythmia.

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